

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Rhythmic Accompaniment Generation with Transformer Neural Networks

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Related Work	5
2.1	Symbolic Music Representations	5
2.1.1	Describing Rhythms	7
2.1.2	Describing Rhythm Pairs	9
2.2	Symbolic Music Generation	11
2.2.1	Sequence-to-Sequence Transformer Models	11
2.2.2	Generating Paired Rhythms	11
2.3	Evaluating Generative Systems	12
2.4	Systems for Automatic Mashup Creation	13
3	Methodology	15
3.1	Data	15
3.1.1	Dataset	15
3.1.2	Parts	15
3.1.3	Representation	16
3.1.4	Tokenization	17
3.2	Model Training	17
3.3	Model Inference	19
3.4	Evaluation	20
4	Results	23

4.1	Melody to Bass	23
4.2	Bass to Melody	25
4.3	Paired Descriptors	26
5	Discussion	29
5.1	Limitations	29
5.2	Future Work	30
	List of Figures	32
	List of Tables	33
	Bibliography	34

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Abstract

Deep learning methods have recently emerged as state-of-the-art for many tasks related to automatic music generation. In particular, research on the task of accompaniment generation has made great advances that have the potential to greatly enhance tools for music production, performance, and education. Much of the work in this domain has focused primarily on generating either harmonic accompaniment or drum accompaniment. This thesis connects tonality and rhythm in an investigation of automatic rhythmic accompaniment for non-drum instruments — given a vocal melody, compose a rhythm for the bass. We create a dataset of multi-part rhythm pairs from the publicly available Lakh MIDI dataset [1] largely comprising contemporary Western music, and use it to train a set of conditional generative models. We evaluate these models using two measures of distribution similarity, overlapping area (OA) and Kullback-Leibler divergence (KLD) [2], to determine their ability to reproduce the aspects of rhythm that we understand to be valuable. Additionally, we explore the use of rhythmic descriptors as methods of representing and understanding the rhythmic relationships between two accompanying rhythms. Our results show that the models are able to generally capture both individual rhythmic properties and relationships between pairs of rhythms in the training dataset. Furthermore, we demonstrate that good results can be achieved even with a relatively small model.

Keywords: Accompaniment Generation; Generative AI; Rhythm; Symbolic Music; Computational Musicology

Chapter 1

Introduction

Accompaniment generation refers to the task of automatically composing musical parts that support or complement a given melody or theme. Generated accompaniment can include chords, bass lines, rhythmic patterns, counter-melodies, or even a combination of all. With recent advances in AI and music research, accompaniment generation systems have been increasingly utilized in music production software, electronic instruments, live performances, and educational applications. In particular, accompaniment generation can be useful for:

- Performance: Allowing a solo musician to sound like a full band
- Practice: Making practice sessions more engaging
- Composition: Bringing song ideas to life

Rhythmic accompaniment generation is a subset of accompaniment generation that focuses specifically on rhythmically supporting a given melody or theme. This sub-task can be particularly useful for scenarios in which rhythmic variations are desired for some fixed harmonic material, for example allowing a music producer to stylistically customize the arpeggiation of a chord progression, as in the chord performance feature in Scaler 2¹. This scenario is easily envisioned in compositional applications, but also occurs in other contexts such as live performance and mashup creation as in CoSo by Splice².

Prior work in the area has predominantly centered around drum machines and percussion-based algorithms. This thesis aims to fill a gap in existing rhythmic accompaniment generation research by exploring the potential and significance of automatically generating rhythms using non-drum instruments such as the guitar, piano, bass, and wind instruments. Specifically, this work focuses on melody, a single distinct sequence of music notes often perceived as a standalone entity. While

¹<https://www.scalerplugin.com/>

²<https://tools.splice.com/coso>

drums undeniably form the skeletal framework of many musical genres, drum accompaniment is generally limited to rhythmic patterns. This is contrasted with melodic instruments which often carry a greater range of tones, allowing for additional musical context such as harmony to be integrated into rhythmic structure. This added richness contributes greatly to the expressive texture of a piece and in turn enables more complex musical interactions to occur between a given melody and accompaniment. As such, rhythmic accompaniment with melodic instruments brings to existing accompaniment generation literature a different set of musical opportunities, expanding the scope of current automated music technology.

Musical compositions are commonly comprised of multiple parts. In multi-part music, each strand or part represents a unique musical identity. If we think of a song as being a combination of multiple musical strands, a part is one of those strands. Figure 1 shows an excerpt of an orchestral pop song with a diverse set of instruments. When we listen to it, we might hear a melody strand made up by the Muted Trumpet and the Vocal Aahs and a harmony strand made up by the Acoustic Guitar and Strings. We refer to each of these strands as a part. These parts come together in a composition to interact with each other, rhythmically and otherwise.

Figure 1: An excerpt from *Tonight* by Leonard Bernstein with a grouping of instruments to parts. Transcription from the Lakh MIDI Dataset [1].

In addition to applied uses, the scope of this work also has implications on music perception. When we listen to music, our brains selectively pay attention to different streams of information [3]. We might focus on a vocalist’s melody while still being aware of an underlying bassline. This cognitive ability to simultaneously process and separate audio streams allows us to appreciate the layers and textures created through interplay between harmony, rhythm, and timbre. At the same time, the Gestalt principles in psychology suggest that humans tend to organize patterns into groups [4]. When the vocalist sings a different rhythm from the bassline, the brain attempts to group them and make sense of the pattern as a whole. This sometimes leads to the perception of a congruent, composite pattern, and at other times leads to the perception of separate, independent rhythms. Understanding how rhythms fit together leads to a myriad of questions. In what ways can rhythms fit together?

How can we model the relationships between rhythms? How do these relationships vary between pairs of parts? Does perception of fit vary across different musical styles? Fundamentally, what do we even mean when we say that two rhythms fit well together? This concept of *fit* is often a subjective and intuitive feeling. In this thesis, we use the term *compatibility* synonymously with *fit*. Instead of envisioning this concept as a binary classification between "fits together" and "does not fit together", we propose imagining the concept as instead a spectrum. For example, rhythms A and B might be seen as fitting better together than rhythms A and C.

Musician Paul Jackson Jr explains one ingredient of fit from the perspective of a funk rhythm guitarist: "Listen to the bassline: where are the holes in it, i.e. where are the places where it is not playing too much? Stay out of the way of it. Provide rhythm just for a pulse. Stand out where the bass isn't standing out" [5]. Generalized versions of this same advice come from the study of musical orchestration, which is centrally concerned with how each part of a musical piece feeds into the entangled whole. A single orchestra piece can be seen as an amalgamation of various different musical parts that all fit well together. Orchestration stresses the importance of defining the lead part versus the accompaniment to reliably guide the focus of a listener's attention [6, 7]. This is conceivably one example method of enforcing musical fit between parts.

In addition to automatically generating rhythmic accompaniment parts with melodic instruments, this thesis also seeks to explore and better understand rhythmic fit between musical parts through the combined perspectives of musicology and machine learning. We distill complex, multi-track musical pieces down to their most basic rhythmic components in an attempt to materially understand the building blocks of rhythmic fit. In order to understand rhythmic compatibility between multiple parts, we will be first examining rhythmic descriptors for a single part. A rhythmic descriptor is a term used to characterize a particular rhythm characteristic that is present in a piece of music. With single-part rhythmic descriptors as foundational blocks, we can go on to extend our understanding by exploring novel ways to describe the rhythmic relationships between multiple parts that fit well together.

With recent advancements in deep learning, generative artificial intelligence (AI) methods have yielded impressive results in music technology research. Generative AI as a field focuses on the automatic creation of new and original content, often with a calibre similar to that of human-created content. In generative AI, sequence-to-sequence (Seq2Seq) transformer models [8, 9] have been shown to be successful at modelling music [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. Seq2Seq transformer models take as input a sequence and return as output another sequence, utilizing various attention mechanisms that allow the model to dynamically focus on specific parts of a sequence. This is said to be similar to the way humans process information, allowing for longer-term dependencies in sequences to be captured in an effective and efficient manner. This makes Seq2Seq transformer models ideal candidates for our task of automatic rhythmic accompaniment generation as rhythms are conventionally represented as linear sequences of notes. We frame our approach as a task of conditional sequence-to-sequence generation: given a source sequence of mu-

sical notes, generate an accompanying sequence of musical notes. Consequently, this thesis evaluates the trained models on their ability to capture rhythmic relationships present in multi-part music.

We begin in [chapter 2](#) by giving a broad overview of prior work in related areas, encompassing studies from the fields of musicology, music information retrieval, and machine learning. In [chapter 3](#) we lay out our methodology and detail the dataset, representations, models, training and inference configurations, and evaluation metrics used, including paired rhythmic descriptors proposed in this thesis. In [chapter 4](#) we present a thorough evaluation of various model and descriptor results. Finally, in [chapter 5](#) we conclude with a discussion of interesting observations and possible future work that could be done to explore this topic further.

The source code for our experiments along with accompanying audio examples are made openly available on GitHub³.

³<https://github.com/p3zo/rhythmic-relationships>

Chapter 2

Related Work

Given that there is not much existing work in modeling rhythmic fit specifically, the literature review presented here consists of the following areas: a study of existing symbolic music representations, terms used to describe single rhythms and relationships between rhythm pairs, state-of-the-art methods for symbolic music generation, evaluation metrics used for these symbolic generative methods, and mashup creation systems. Descriptors for rhythmic relationships are explored as a proxy to rhythmic fit as rhythmic fit is not a well-studied concept in current literature. Mashup creation systems are included in the review as an adjacent area to modeling rhythmic compatibility as mashups are composed by recombining pieces of music or parts of them that fit well together. In this chapter, we enumerate various approaches to each aforementioned area from multiple perspectives and provide an overview of existing related work.

2.1 Symbolic Music Representations

There are multiple ways to represent music. A commonly used music representation is audio, an acoustic representation of music as waveforms that can be stored and reproduced as air pressure waves for our ears to hear. Audio is stored as a sequence of samples that encode sound waves. Performing experiments and analysis on audio music representations typically involves computational processing to extract the relevant features as sequences of audio samples are not necessarily human-readable. Audio representations are capable of capturing acoustic information that is only present at performance time, such as ambient noises and background voices. The richness and completeness of musical information encapsulated in audio representations makes them prime choices for information retrieval tasks like music genre classification and music recommendation.

Symbolic representations are an alternative way of representing music through the use of standardized musical notation comprising some set of abstract symbols or elements. Examples of symbolic music representations include sheet music used to describe instrument scores and the Musical Instrument Digital Interface (MIDI)

protocol and format. Unlike audio, symbolic music can only contain musical information that can be represented by the available notation symbols. Consequently, symbolic representations offer benefits such as file size compactness and computational ease of parsing compared to audio representations, thus making it a popular choice for tasks pertaining to automatic music analysis and generation.

The MIDI format offers a way of storing music as a sequence of events or messages that encode musical context including notes, pitch, velocity, duration, and onset changes. Much work has built upon MIDI's event-based representations. The MIDI-like representation [24] converts MIDI messages to tokens usable as input to a model. Representations like REMI [25], Compound Word [26], and OctupleMIDI [27] extend the format to include structural and time with *bar* and *position* tokens. The HVO format [28, 29] encodes rhythmic micro-timings useful for modeling unquantized instrumental performances. Several open access tools exist for interchanging between formats [30, 31, 32]. Each of these variations of symbolic representations provides a slightly different view into rhythmic relationships.

Figure 2: Onset vectors. Figure from [33].

Figure 3: Examples of event-based representations for a musical excerpt. Figure from [32].

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate a few symbolic representations of differing richness. The former features a very simple representation: a 1-dimensional vector encoding only the onset positions of notes. This is contrasted against the latter figure which shows two event-based representations that encode onsets alongside musical context such as pitch, velocity, duration, and tempo, as well as long-term structural information like bar lines.

There exists a trade-off between representation richness and model complexity as richer representations contain more information, leading to the need for more complex models that are equipped to process larger amounts of data. It is important to consider the specific types of musical information we care about for the task of conditionally generating compatible rhythms to inform the selection of an optimal representation. In this work, we are not concerned with modeling structure, repetition, grooves, or microtimings.

2.1.1 Describing Rhythms

Rhythms are naturally occurring in many domains aside from music including linguistics [34], psychology [35], and sociology [36]. The ubiquitous nature of rhythms means that they can be characterized and described from a variety of perspectives ranging from categorizations to frameworks to informal observations from musicians. From a musicological perspective, Cooper [37] provides a framing of various ways in which rhythmic units can become perceptually coherent when played simultaneously. Toussaint [33] defines geometric structures such as "necklaces" and "bracelets" that provide a mathematical framework for categorizing and comparing rhythms based on their inter-onset intervals.

When it comes to analyzing a single rhythm, many different types of measures can be used. Figure 4 shows a comprehensive table of 29 descriptors for 6 different rhythms that are used in many styles of music from around the world. Some of these descriptors like syncopation and off-beatness are natively musical and designed specifically to describe rhythms. Many are borrowed from other domains like information theory and geometry. Toussaint [33] demonstrated that an array of descriptors like the one in Figure 4 can be used to characterize one family of rhythms as being distinct from others.

Among these descriptors are a few measures we consider particularly relevant to this thesis:

- **Density:** For monophonic rhythmic patterns, the density is simply defined as the number of onsets present in the pattern.
- **Syncopation:** Defined as a disruption of a regular rhythmic flow, achieved by stressing or accenting a weak beat, or by de-emphasizing a strong beat.
- **Balance:** Defined by Milne and Herff [38] as the proximity of a rhythm's *center* to the centre of the unit circle. A rhythm's center is defined as the mean sequence position of its onsets.

- Evenness: Defined by [39] as how well-distributed the onsets within a rhythm are.

While these descriptors give us valuable methods for describing individual rhythms, they are not directly transferable to rhythm pairs. We thus require an additional set of metrics to describe rhythmic relationships.

Property	Shiko	Son	Soukous	Rumba	Bossa	Gahu
Maximal Evenness	-	-	-	-	Yes	-
Centroid Balance	8.0	1.6	8.0	9.0	8.0	14.7
Swap-distance	4	5	6	4	6	7
Evenness						
Rhythmic Oddity	-	Yes	-	Yes	Yes	-
Rhythmic Oddity Amount	6	7	5	5	6	4
Off-Beatness	0	1	2	2	2	1
Weighted Off-Beatness	2	4	6	5	6	5
Metrical Complexity	2	4	6	5	6	5
Keith Syncopation	1	2	4	2	3	3
Pressing Complexity	6	14.5	15	17	19.5	22
Entropy-Adjacent	0.97	1.52	1.92	1.52	1.52	0.72
Entropy-Full	1.84	2.24	2.72	2.44	2.72	1.84
nPVI	66.7	40.5	70.5	41.0	23.8	14.3
Closure	Yes	Yes	-	Yes	-	-
Main-Beat Onsets	3	2	1	2	1	1
Distinct Durations	4	5	7	6	4	7
Distinct Adjacent Durations	2	3	4	3	2	3
Onset Distinct Distances	16	16	17	19	16	17
Deep	Yes	-	-	-	Yes	-
Shallowness	0	4	6	4	0	6
Tallness	4	3	2	3	4	2
Swap-Distance Centrality	10	6	10	11	8	12
Mirror Symmetry	Yes	Yes	-	-	Yes	-
Diagonal Mirror Symmetry	-	Yes	-	-	-	-
Pulse Sub Symmetries	29	25	25	24	28	28
IOI Sub Symmetries	4	2	1	1	4	2
Area of Phase Space Polygons	2.0	1.5	5.0	2.0	0.5	2.5
Fractal Metric Hierarchy	-	Yes	-	-	-	-
Shadow Contour Isomorphism	-	Yes	-	-	-	-

Figure 4: 29 descriptors for six distinguished rhythms. Figure from [33].

2.1.2 Describing Rhythm Pairs

Few if any descriptors for rhythmic fit exist, but there are several metrics for describing general rhythmic relationships that we can learn from.

Firstly, Lefebvre’s methodology of *Rhythmanalysis* [40] observes that rhythms in many domains align according to four categories: consonantly, dissonantly, neutrally, or equally.

Ames [41] builds up a rudimentary set of rhythmic components into multiple rhythmic grammars and explores the generation of multiple types of complementary rhythms: stratified rhythms, mixed rhythms, interlaced rhythms, roles, leading rhythms, and leading phrases. These are encoded in an application called the Complementary Rhythm Generator.

Another relational framework for rhythms is the *rhythm space*, which is a multi-dimensional space in which rhythms are positioned according to similarity. These spaces can be constructed using any type of rhythm (monophonic, polyphonic, performed on drum or piano) and arbitrary dimensionality, and are used primarily to study the perception of rhythm similarity [42, 43, 44]. Rhythm spaces can also be converted from discrete spaces composed of known patterns into continuous spaces in which new rhythmic patterns can be interpolated from empty regions [45].

Similarity

Toussaint [33] applies a variety of general sequence similarity measures from non-musical domains to musical rhythms. For example:

- Hamming distance: The number of positions where the two sequences differ.
- Edit distance: The minimum number of edits necessary to convert one sequence to the other.
- Swap distance: The minimum number of swaps needed to transform one rhythm into the other.
- Directed swap distance: The minimum number of swaps needed to convert the denser rhythm into the sparser rhythm.

These measures are used extensively in information theory, geometry, and other domains such as computational biology in which the directed swap distance is used to measure the similarity between DNA molecules [46]. Edit distances can be applied in a musical context as shown in Figure 5. While similarity measures can be used to describe a pair of rhythms, they are not directly indicators of compatibility — two rhythms that are very similar do not necessarily fit together well. Furthermore, these distance based similarity metrics do not account for cognitive rhythm concepts such as syncopation, meter, and pulse.

Figure 5: The edit distance between the *clave son* and the *fume-fume* rhythm is 4. Figure from [33].

Temporal Relation

Another method of describing the relationship between two rhythms is to observe how they overlap temporally. James Allen's interval algebra [47] introduces a classification of 13 temporal relations between any two sequences as illustrated in Figure 6. Recently, Sigler proposed a generalized version of Allen's intervals in a musical setting to visualize musical structure, creating permuted scores as in Figure 7 that are colored and annotated with these relations, elucidating the sections that make up an overall structure of a score [48]. While there are no quantitative descriptors for temporal relations provided by these authors, this thesis takes inspiration from these works to design one.

precedes	meets	overlaps	finished by	contains	started by	equals
preceded by	met by	overlapped by	finishes	during	starts	

Figure 6: An illustration from [48] showing the 13 classes of temporal relations defined by Allen [47].

Figure 7: A visualization from [48] illustrating an excerpt from Haydn String Quartet Op. 17 No. 3 Mvt. 1, reorganized to show the structure of a graph created using temporal relations between notes.

Complementarity

Morris [49] defines two rhythms as complementary if one rhythm contains onsets in the silent pulses of the other. Toussaint notes that when a rhythm and its complement are played simultaneously in the same cycle with only a slight difference in timbre or intensity, it can sound like the two rhythms are continuously switching between the foreground and the background of the listener’s cognitive attention. This same property was used by Arnold Schoenberg as a compositional tool in the pitch domain [50], leading us to consider its possible usefulness for generating compatible compositions in the rhythm domain.

2.2 Symbolic Music Generation

2.2.1 Sequence-to-Sequence Transformer Models

The aim of generative modeling is to estimate the probabilistic process of producing an observation in a given dataset. This estimation can then be employed to generate new observations. Applying generative models to music has a long history, but recent language-based approaches to symbolic music generation have shown unprecedented potential in capturing the intricacies in various music features including long-term structure, repetition, and most interestingly to this thesis, interdependencies between multiple instruments in a piece [10, 15]. These capabilities are largely due to the attention mechanism of the transformer model which allows it to weight the relevance of different parts of the input for each generated element or token in the output sequence [9]. This makes it effective for tasks where the input and output sequences can have complex relationships in temporal structure, such as in our task of modeling relationships between pairs of rhythms.

Specifically, the use of Seq2Seq transformer models have produced state-of-the-art results in automatic music generation [10, 11, 51, 12, 13]. Seq2Seq models [8] contain an encoder that is responsible for converting the input sequence into a fixed-length context vector. This is done by passing the input sequence through various neural network layers and self-attention mechanisms to identify and extract the core features of the input sequence. The resulting context vector is then passed to a decoder who is responsible for producing an output sequence. The decoder similarly utilizes various layers and self-attention mechanisms. Generation of the output sequence occurs one element or token at a time in a step-wise fashion. Each generation step is often conditioned on the output of all previous steps. By attaching an encoder to a decoder, Seq2Seq models are able to learn the core nuances in the relationships between input and output sequences, leading to remarkable results in the field of music generation.

2.2.2 Generating Paired Rhythms

Among the growing body of literature leveraging transformer-based architectures, a number of works have done so for the task of multi-track music generation [52, 15, 14, 27, 16]. These works can be broadly grouped into two categories in the context of this

thesis. The first category is multi-track models that simultaneously generate music for one or multiple instruments. In contrast to the approaches representing music as separate sequences of events for separate tracks, works of this category have demonstrated the feasibility of concatenating several tracks into a single sequence in order to model multi-track music. These works include a mix of approaches using VAEs [53, 54], GANs [55, 56], and autoregressive models [17, 18, 19, 20]. As multi-track music generation is a complex endeavor involving many nuanced relationships, the second category of works break down the problem into smaller, conditional generation tasks. These tasks include generating chordal accompaniments for monophonic melodies [57, 58], generating monophonic melodies for existing chords [59], generating melody based on vocal rhythms [60], continuing rhythmic patterns [61, 22], and generating drum accompaniments to existing material [62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 29, 67, 68]. Some works also leverage hierarchical principles of music structure to combine these tasks in sequence [69]. The Cyber-João system [70] seeks to generate an accompanying guitar rhythm given a melody and chords in bossa nova music. Haki et al. [29] use a rhythmic representation with micro-timing to train a drum generation model focused on a real-time scenario, which largely learns to reinforce an incoming groove. Parallel work [71] explored instrument-specific generation that would help the system to complement the input rhythm.

Across both categories of works, the rhythmic relationships learned by models and their corresponding evaluation are generally not explored. By virtue of conditionally modeling the distributions of existing rhythms all of these works are implicitly modeling rhythmic compatibility to varying extents. However, none of these works explicitly take compatibility as a main focus, study the conditional relationships learned by the models, or take the relationships between parts into consideration.

2.3 Evaluating Generative Systems

Multiple frameworks have been proposed for the objective statistical evaluation of generated music [72, 2, 11]. Frameworks have also been proposed to instead evaluate the subjective attributes of these models such as creativity, originality, and effectiveness [73, 74]. While many evaluative frameworks have been studied from both objective and subjective perspectives, there is no one single standardized method of evaluating generative music [75].

One notable method for objective evaluation is to compare samples that are generated by models with samples that are present in the training dataset. Yang and Lerch [2] propose a framework of inducing and comparing distributions of descriptors between a model’s output and its training set. Their framework begins with two collections of samples as inputs: a set of ground-truth observations from a training dataset, and a set of generated samples from a model trained on that dataset. They propose to compute a set of features for each sample that is rooted in some piece of musical domain knowledge that is understood to be valuable to the task at hand. From these features, they apply pairwise exhaustive cross-validation to compute the distance of every sample to every other sample, yielding a set of distance histograms. These pairwise distances are computed both within a single dataset

or between datasets and are referred to as *intra-set* and *inter-set* distances respectively. The intra-set distance measures can be used to show whether the model has captured the full variety of the training samples. The inter-set distances can be used to show whether the model has generated samples that are similar to the training samples.

From these distances, the probability density function (PDF) of each feature histogram is estimated by kernel density estimation [76]. These PDFs allow for the computation of relative measurements comparing the two distributions. That comparison can be quantified using two measures: Kullback-Leibler divergence (KLD) and overlapping area (OA). KLD is the most common measure of how much two distributions diverge. A high value means they diverge a lot, and a low value means the distributions closely match. OA takes on values between 0 and 1, where 1 means the two distributions are exactly the same. This measure is used to provide additional context to the KLD because KLD is unbounded and asymmetric. The comparison of these measures can provide useful insights on both the training dataset properties and the characteristics of the generative system.

2.4 Systems for Automatic Mashup Creation

Mashup creation refers to the practice of combining segments of musical material from different sources into a new piece. SingSong [77] represents the state-of-the-art in audio segment combination, using a Transformer-XL architecture to generate instrumental music to accompany the provided input vocals. A limitation of this work is that it is in the audio domain and therefore relies on algorithms for transcribing and extracting features from audio. This can be a difficult task, may introduce errors that affect the quality of the output, and, for musicological or compositional purposes, presents less flexibility than systems operating in the symbolic domain. For example, in compositional applications, making fine-grained edits to the generated audio output involves significantly more work.

Many approaches for determining compatibility between segments for mashup systems have been explored that include explicitly modeled harmonic features [78] as well as rhythmic features [79, 80]. However, in considering the relationship of the component rhythmic features, these works have taken into account only similarity, disregarding the fact that two musical segments with very dissimilar rhythms can fit well together.

Although works such as Neural Loop Combiner [81] acknowledge that it is possible for two music segments to fit well together despite having different rhythms, few works have attempted to explicitly model rhythmic fit from data. Huang et al. [82] is one such work, in which the authors train a model to predict the "mashability" of two given audio clips. In their subjective evaluation of the model, they ask participants to provide ratings for rhythmic compatibility between the vocal parts and the vocal accompaniments. These rating annotations could potentially be a suitable foundation for exploring the attributes of rhythms that give rise to compatibility. Although the authors do not explore this line of inquiry, they demonstrate that

mashup creation systems could provide a fertile ground for the subjective evaluation of rhythmic compatibility. By the same token, models of rhythmic compatibility in the symbolic domain could be useful for creating new and flexible automatic mashup creation systems.

Chapter 3

Methodology

With the concepts and questions introduced in the introduction and related work sections in mind, we design a set of experiments focused around modeling automatic rhythmic accompaniment generation with non-drum instruments in multi-part music with the objective of capturing and learning rhythmic relationships between pairs of rhythms. This section starts by detailing the data pipeline used, continues with the model training and inference process, and finishes with the evaluation metrics employed.

3.1 Data

3.1.1 Dataset

As there are no existing publicly available datasets for rhythmic fit, our approach opts for using co-occurrence as a stand-in for compatibility under the assumption that rhythms that are played together in published songs usually fit well together. We construct a dataset of paired rhythms between multiple parts using a subset of the Lakh MIDI Dataset [1] as our data source. The Lakh MIDI Dataset is a collection of 176,581 unique MIDI files, each of which contains a multi-track recording of a musical piece. It primarily consists of contemporary western music that is mostly pop, rock, and jazz. This thesis specifically uses the clean MIDI subset containing about 17,000 multi-track MIDI files. The clean MIDI subset was curated to deliver higher data quality than the full Lakh dataset, making it more ideal for experiments and analysis.

3.1.2 Parts

As defined in [chapter 1](#), the *parts* in a multi-track musical composition are the strands of melody or harmony that make up the overall musical texture. The grouping of instruments into parts depends heavily on the musical style, so one must be careful to define a set of parts according to a style. For example, the cavaquinho is a Portuguese instrument that resembles a small guitar that would play the role of a

harmonic instrument in many styles; however, in Brazilian Choro music it typically plays a primarily percussive role [83]. Many musical styles revolve around somewhat uniform instrumentations where each instrument plays a specific role in the composition. For electronic music, the following parts have been proposed by prior work: chords, melody, effects, bass, and percussion [84, 85]. For styles like pop, rock, or jazz, a more appropriate list of parts might instead be *percussive*, *bassline*, *harmonic*, and *melodic*.

Since there is no public dataset available with part labels, we use the instrumental categories from the General MIDI spec (Level 2)¹ as a proxy. In particular, we follow the methodology of MusicVAE [53] which defines three parts to model multi-stream music: drums, bass, and melody. We ignore drums and add Synth Lead [81, 88] to the melody part. The resulting parts used in our experiments are thus:

- Bass (programs [33, 40])
- Melody (programs [1, 32], [81, 88])

Additionally, in a multi-track MIDI file with multiple instruments for a given part, we retain only the first track for each part.

3.1.3 Representation

To get the data into a format that we can input to a transformer, we first convert the MIDI to a 2D array known as a *piano roll*, in which each row corresponds to a pitch, each column corresponds to a time slice, and each value is a MIDI velocity. We quantize the piano rolls to 16th notes and use the MIDI note-off events to discard note duration information, preserving only the onset of each note. We then slice each track into overlapping 2-bar segments. We determined bar boundaries using the encoded tempos and removed segments identified as having non-4/4 time signatures. To remove segments without melody or bass lines, we follow the melody extraction pipeline used in MusicVAE [53] and keep only monophonic segments that meet the following criteria:

- 4 beats per bar
- At least 2 pitches
- At most 1 bar of consecutive rests

Our final dataset contains approximately 550k bass-melody pairs. We flatten the resulting monophonic piano rolls into 1-dimensional vectors and refer to these unpitched arrays as *onset vectors*.

¹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/General_MIDI_Level_2

3.1.4 Tokenization

We convert the onset vectors into sequences of discrete tokens using the vocabulary shown in Table 1. We group velocities into 5 different bins and assign a token to each bin. Our bins divide the MIDI velocity range $[0, 127]$ into 5, with the exception of 0 velocity: 0, 1-32, 33-64, 65-96, and 97-127. As we are working exclusively with onsets, the note-off token is omitted. We also reserve a special token to indicate the start of a sequence. This tokenization approach gives us a representation with a total vocabulary size of 6: 5 velocity bins and a start-of-sequence token. As such, we represent the monophonic melodies and basslines as sequences of 16th note events.

Token	MIDI Velocity	Description
0	-	start
1	0	rest
2	(1-32]	<i>p</i>
3	(33-64]	<i>mp</i>
4	(65-96]	<i>mf</i>
5	(97-127]	<i>f</i>

Table 1: The vocabulary used to tokenize onset vectors.

Our goal is to train a model that is able to pick up on rhythmic relationships in the data, but it remains unknown exactly what features or elements will help the model best achieve that. Given this limitation, our approach on tokenizing the model inputs focuses on distilling the data down to only the most essential rhythmic information: onset times and velocities. The rationale for this decision is to start with the bare minimum, allowing for incremental additions to be made subsequently to observe how each addition changes what the model learns.

3.2 Model Training

For a set of tokens $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_T)$, the transformer model learns the joint probability $P(\mathbf{x})$, autoregressively expressed as:

$$P(\mathbf{x}) = \prod_t P(x_t | x_{<t})$$

Figure 8: Overview architecture of our sequence-to-sequence transformer model.

The model architecture of our implemented Seq2Seq transformer model is shown in Figure 8. The tokenized representation of a source rhythm — a melody part in this specific example, is first passed through a source embedding layer and a positional embedding layer. The resulting vector is then fed as input to the encoder which produces another set of embeddings that are forwarded to the decoder. The decoder generates an accompanying output rhythm one token at a time. In order for it to choose the best token to generate at each step, it needs to learn the likelihood of each next token. It is thus necessary for the decoder to have access to information contained within the target rhythm — a bass part in our example. This enables the model to train in an autoregressive manner: it decomposes the probability distribution of the entire target sequence into the product of conditional distributions of each onset, considering all previously generated tokens in the output sequence as input context for generating the next token. Notably, we shift the input target sequence to the decoder by one position to the right. This helps improve model generation quality and increase model stability by mimicking model constraints that exist at inference time, allowing the model to learn to perform stepwise generation well. If the decoder only sees ground truth tokens at training time, the model is likely to struggle more at inference time with generation that is in part conditioned upon self-generated tokens. Additionally, we prepend a start token to the shifted-by-1 target token representation to form a context vector. The start token helps signal to the decoder that it is time to start generating. Similar to the source vector, this context vector is passed through a context embedding layer and a positional embedding layer. A causal attention mask is applied to the resulting vector to prevent the model from seeing target tokens that occur in the future when learning the token distribution at each time step. This mask is only necessary for the target sequence as the model will always be given the entire source sequence in our task of conditionally generating an accompanying rhythm.

Using this architecture, we train two models: a melody-to-bass model for mapping melodic rhythms to bassline rhythms, and a bass-to-melody model for the converse

direction. Both models are trained with identical architectures and hyperparameter configurations. The selection of hyperparameters was based on a combination of subjective evaluation of the output and perplexity of the predictions during training. Perplexity is a common measure for evaluating the performance of autoregressive models, defined as:

$$PPL(X) = \exp \left(-\frac{1}{t} \sum_i \log p_{\theta}(x_i | x_{<i}) \right)$$

Conceptually, this can be thought of as the average log-likelihood of a token given its preceding context. A model is considered effective if it has a high log-likelihood, leading to a lower perplexity. We stop model training when the validation perplexity ceases to decrease and take the model from this point forward to use for experimentation.

Both the encoder and decoder were composed with 4 layers of transformer blocks and 3 attention heads. Each layer was parameterized with an embedding size of 144. Both models were trained with batch sizes of 128 using a cross-entropy loss with a learning rate of 1e-5. The data is split into train, test, and validation sets with respective sizes of 90%, 5%, and 5% of the total data.

3.3 Model Inference

A distribution of token probabilities such as the one seen in [Figure 9](#) can be sampled in a variety of ways to generate an output sequence of tokens. Research in natural language processing has demonstrated that the quality of generations from trained autoregressive language models is significantly influenced by the sampling strategy that is used [86]. We experiment with a few different sampling strategies to see how they capture rhythmic relationships differently. In particular, we use three sampling methods: greedy, multinomial, and nucleus. In greedy sampling, the token with the highest probability is selected at each step. We use greedy sampling as a baseline for comparison. However, non-deterministic sampling methods are desirable for our use-case as we would ideally like to generate different accompaniments given the same input for variety. For example, a user of a compositional application might want to listen to multiple generated accompaniments for the same source music before selecting the one that works best for them. Multinomial sampling uniformly samples from the probability distribution of next tokens. Nucleus sampling first truncates the distribution to the smallest set of tokens whose cumulative probability exceeds a threshold probability p , then samples from that truncated distribution.

Figure 9: A distribution of language token probabilities. Figure from <https://huggingface.co/blog/how-to-generate>.

An additional parameter used during sampling is the *temperature*. This parameter modulates the probability distributions of the output tokens and dictates the extent to which the generated rhythms are consistent over time. A temperature of 1 uses the unmodulated probabilities and is the default behavior. A temperature of > 1 compresses the probability distributions, making less probable tokens more probable, effectively making the samples more random. Conversely, a temperature > 0 and < 1 sharpens the probability distributions, making the most probable tokens even more probable, effectively making the samples more deterministic.

3.4 Evaluation

We evaluate our models with two primary motivations. First, we are concerned with the models' ability to generate coherent rhythms. Second, we wish to examine the relationships between each generated rhythm and its conditioning material.

We carry out these evaluations using the framework proposed by Yang and Lerch [2] for comparing distributions between the model output and the training set across various rhythm descriptors as detailed in section 2.3. To make these comparisons we use two sets of descriptors, one to describe individual rhythms and the other to describe the relationships between a pair of rhythms.

For each model we compare the distributions of the descriptors of the generated samples to the distributions of the descriptors of the training set. Following Yang and Lerch [2], we compute the pairwise distance distributions between the set of training samples and the combined set of training and generated samples for each descriptor. For the bass-to-melody model, we randomly select 100 melodies from the training dataset and generate 100 samples of melodies with both models using each sampling technique: greedy, multinomial, and nucleus. We do the same, vice-

versa, for the melody-to-bass model. All samples are taken using *temperature* = 1, and nucleus samples are made with $p = 0.92$. Further details regarding the various sampling techniques are introduced in [section 3.3](#). Additionally, we generate 100 samples of melody/bass/drums trios with MusicVAE [53] to serve as a baseline for our evaluation. We select this model as a baseline because we closely followed its methodology when choosing parts (see [subsection 3.1.2](#)) and extracting melodies from MIDI (see [subsection 3.1.3](#)). Specifically we use 4-bar trios model from MusicVAE which was trained over 9.4 million trios of melody, bass, and drum parts from 1.5 million MIDI files, including the full Lakh MIDI dataset. Similar to ours, their training set also removed segments with non-4/4 time signatures and quantized to 16-note resolution.

We compute the set of individual rhythm descriptors for all the generated rhythms, followed by the set of paired descriptors for all the generated rhythms with their corresponding training rhythms. As the baseline model generates bass and melody simultaneously, we compute the paired descriptors using the generated pairs. We then compute the OA and KLD metrics introduced in [section 2.3](#) for each set of resulting samples.

For our set of individual rhythm descriptors, we choose to compute density, syncopation, balance, and evenness. (see [subsection 2.1.1](#)). Validating that the output distributions of these individual rhythm descriptors match those in the training set helps us ensure that the model is generating rhythms like the ones present in the training set.

In addition to the individual rhythm descriptors, we also propose a novel set of descriptors for pairs of rhythms aimed at capturing different types of rhythmic relationships. These paired descriptors will give insight into whether the model is generating rhythms with relationships to the conditioning material like the relationships present in the training set. Specifically, we strive to define measures that are indicative of how well-distributed the combined rhythm is across the pair, both temporally and in terms of density. We propose the use of two novel measures: *onset balance* and *antiphony*, as a set of paired rhythm descriptors.

Onset balance

The onset balance descriptor is designed to give a notion of how similar a pair of rhythms is in terms of density. It is computed as 1 minus the normalized difference in density divided by the pair density. Formally, for a pair of rhythms A and B,

$$\text{OnsetBalance}(A, B) = 1 - \frac{|\text{density}_A - \text{density}_B|}{\text{density}_A + \text{density}_B}$$

Antiphony

Antiphony is intended to answer the question: “How call-responsive is the pair?” It is computed by taking the absolute difference between the rhythm centers (see [sub-](#)

section 2.1.1) divided by the maximum possible difference in centers. This measure takes inspiration from the temporal intervals introduced in subsection 2.1.2. For a pair of rhythms A and B,

$$\text{Antiphony}(A, B) = \frac{|\text{center}_A - \text{center}_B|}{\text{minCenter}_A + \text{maxCenter}_B}$$

where *minCenter* calculates the triangular number² of a rhythm's density divided by its density, and *maxCenter* is the number of steps in a rhythm minus its minimum center.

To compute these rhythm descriptors, we use the Rhythm Toolbox³, an open-source Python library for extracting musical features from symbolic rhythms [45]. The library was originally developed for the study of 16-beat polyphonic drum patterns, but throughout this work we expanded it to support monophonic rhythms of arbitrary length from non-drum instruments. As we needed to compute many descriptors over a large dataset, we made a number of significant performance improvements to the toolbox including speed-ups of around 8500X. We also made the toolbox easy to use for non-drum instruments, arbitrary sequence lengths, and several different representations. As an additional contribution, our proposed descriptors for paired rhythms will also be added to the toolbox.

²https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triangular_number

³<https://github.com/danielgomezmarin/rhythmttoolbox>

Chapter 4

Results

Evaluations of the melody to bass and bass to melody models detailed in [chapter 3](#) are presented below. Audio examples of the model output are available online for listening¹.

4.1 Melody to Bass

Three examples of generated bass rhythms from the melody to bass (MTB) model are shown in [Figure 10](#).

Figure 10: Input melodic rhythms (top) with generated bass rhythms (bottom).

The distributions of the individual rhythm descriptors between the generated samples and the training set are compared in [Figure 11](#). We observe that the distributions are roughly matching across all individual descriptors, albeit with some obvious differences. First, it is clear that the training distributions are multi-modal while the generated distributions are unimodal or bimodal across all descriptors. The relative smoothness of the generated distributions is explained by the fact that only 100 samples were used to create the generated distributions, while 10,000 samples were used to compute the distributions for the training set. Despite this sample

¹<https://github.com/p3zo/rhythmic-relationships>

size imbalance, we can clearly see that the peaks of the generated distributions are mostly closely aligned with those of the training distributions.

Figure 11: Descriptor distributions for training set bass rhythms ($n = 10000$) vs generated bass rhythms ($n = 100$) for the MTB model with nucleus sampling (top) and the baseline model (bottom).

A glaring exception is for syncopation from the MTB model: the generated rhythms are consistently and significantly more syncopated than the rhythms in the training set. In fact, we can see that there are many basslines in the training set that have no syncopation at all; meanwhile, a vanishingly small portion of the generated basslines have no syncopation. The syncopations of basslines from the baseline model more closely match those in the training set, though they do appear to have a longer

tail of high-syncopation rhythms. Other discrepancies in the distribution extremities occur in the balance and evenness comparisons. While the training set rhythms often have balances and evenness near the minimum and maximum values, the generated rhythms tend to take on more middling values. For the density distributions, the MTB samples have a similar bimodal shape to the training set. On the other hand, the distribution of densities from the baseline model samples takes on a unimodal shape.

We can quantify these comparisons using the KL-Divergence (KLD) and Overlapping Area (OA) measures introduced in [section 2.3](#). These measures are reported as an average of the values for each descriptor, for each model and sampling method in [Table 2](#). Recall that a lower KLD is desirable as it means that the distributions have less divergence. Conversely, a higher OA is desirable as it means that the distributions are more overlapping. We can see that the baseline model achieves the highest overlapping area. Not too far behind is the nucleus sampling method from the MTB model. Multinomial sampling also produces reasonable results, with an OA within 5% of the nucleus sampling method. Greedy sampling performs the worst of all methods.

Method	KLD	OA
MusicVAE [53]	0.034	0.880
Greedy	0.161	0.736
Multinomial	0.028	0.785
Nucleus	0.020	0.819

Table 2: Pairwise distribution similarity measures for generated bass rhythms, averaged across all descriptors.

4.2 Bass to Melody

Examples of generated melodic rhythms from the bass to melody (BTM) model are shown in [Figure 12](#).

Figure 12: Input bass rhythms (top row) with generated melodic rhythms (bottom row).

The distributions of the individual rhythm descriptors between the generated samples and the training set are compared in [Figure 13](#). We see that this model also

tends to generate significantly more syncopated rhythms. We also see the same patterns of middling values in balance and evenness as in the MTB model. For densities, the distributions of the BTM model and the baseline model are reversed from before — this time, the baseline rhythms have a slightly bimodal distribution while the BTM model is mostly unimodal.

Figure 13: Descriptor distributions for training set melodic rhythms ($n=10000$) vs generated melodic rhythms ($n=100$) for the BTM model with nucleus sampling (top) and the baseline model (bottom).

The average OAs and KLDs across all individual descriptors for generated melodies are reported in [Table 3](#). We see again that the multinomial and nucleus sampling methods are very similar, with nucleus being again just slightly better. Surprisingly,

a greedy sampling strategy has the highest overlapping area. In fact, it seems suspiciously high, especially alongside a KLD that is also comparatively high. Upon listening to the samples, we find that they are very uniform. Many of them contain just one or two downbeats at the start of a bar, with the rest of the beats silent; some are straight quarter notes with an occasional eighth note. We submit that this disproportionate number of basic rhythms inflate the OA measure because it creates a distribution that is largely contained within that of the training set, as the training set contains many of these basic rhythms as well. Ignoring the greedy OA, we observe that the baseline again generates the rhythms that most closely match the training set.

Method	KLD	OA
MusicVAE [53]	0.034	0.880
Greedy	0.379	0.952
Multinomial	0.221	0.767
Nucleus	0.204	0.788

Table 3: Pairwise distribution similarity measures for generated melodic rhythms, averaged across all descriptors.

4.3 Paired Descriptors

Figure 14 compares the distributions of the paired rhythm descriptors between the training set, the baseline, and our models. We observe that the training set has unimodal distributions for both onset balance and antiphony. All models appear to broadly capture these distributions with varying degrees of skew and kurtosis.

For onset balance, both the baseline and BTM models are centered around the same values as the training set. The MTB model is skewed towards higher values, suggesting that it produces more balanced onsets between melody and bass. Notably, the training distribution has a clear peak at 1, indicating that many of the rhythm pairs are perfectly balanced. All models are missing this peak, with the baseline and BTM models instead having peaks around 0.8, indicating that most of the generated rhythm pairs have at least some onset imbalance.

For antiphony, the training set distribution is concentrated around low values, with a clear peak at 0. Again we observe that no model captures this peak, instead peaking around 0.1 and having relatively few values at exactly 0. The distribution produced by the BTM model is most similar to the training set but slightly broader. The MTB and baseline models are both wider than the BTM, indicating that they produce a wider range of antiphonal interactions, with the MTB model producing the widest distribution.

Referencing Table 4 for the quantitative metrics, we see that all methods have very high overlapping areas and very low divergence, with the exception of greedy sampling from the MTB model. We note again that greedy samples from the BTM

Figure 14: Paired descriptor distributions for melody and bass rhythm pairs from the training set ($n=10000$) vs each model ($n=100$).

model have a very high overlapping area due to their basic nature. The multinomial, nucleus, and baseline methods appear to all be similarly capable of matching the rhythmic relationships of the training set.

Method	KLD	OA
MusicVAE [53]	0.035	0.952
MTB - Greedy	0.084	0.648
MTB - Multinomial	0.009	0.945
MTB - Nucleus	0.005	0.956
BTM - Greedy	0.001	0.98
BTM - Multinomial	0.044	0.939
BTM - Nucleus	0.004	0.957

Table 4: Pairwise distribution similarity measures for melody-bass pairs, averaged across all paired descriptors.

Chapter 5

Discussion

We have presented an evaluation of transformer neural networks for the task of rhythmic accompaniment generation. To our knowledge, there was no such evaluation of a music generation system that focused on rhythmic compatibility prior to this thesis. The results show that our models are generally able to capture the rhythmic properties present in the training dataset, and that good results can be achieved even with a relatively small model trained over only 550k rhythm pairs.

Qualitatively, the models produce accompaniment rhythms that sound compatible with their input. Quantitatively, the models are capable of generating both individual rhythms that closely approximate those in the training set as well as accompanying rhythms that relate to the conditioning material in a way that closely approximates the relationships present in the training set.

Our experiments with sampling strategies reveal that nucleus sampling consistently yields the best results, followed closely by multinomial sampling. For both models, nucleus and multinomial sampling strategies seem to work equally well. Greedy sampling does not work well in either case, despite having apparently good objective metrics. For both models, greedy sampling produces basic, uninteresting rhythms characterized by very low density, no syncopation, and onsets falling only on the strong beats.

5.1 Limitations

We observe that both the MTB and BTM models struggle with syncopation. Both models generate rhythms that tend to be significantly more syncopated than the rhythms in the training set. The baseline model, on the other hand, is perfectly capable of capturing realistic syncopation. It is possible that the hyperparameters we selected for training are limiting the model’s ability to improve during training. Fine-tuning hyperparameters or training on a larger dataset could help lead to a more robust model that produces less syncopated rhythms.

We do not consider pitched representations in our experiments. We would like to

experiment with a representation that preserves pitch, motivated by the hypothesis that pitch and rhythm are deeply intertwined. This hypothesis is supported by findings that show harmonic information is useful for the task of downbeat tracking [87].

We also do not distinguish between rhythms with repeated notes and their simplified versions, as shown in Figure 15. As this perceptual nuance is a frequent occurrence in our dataset, handling it appropriately could lead to better results.

Figure 15: Two bass rhythms that are perceptually similar, with repeated notes preserved (left) and removed (right).

Finally, we train models that are relatively small in both complexity and dataset size. Still, the performance of these models approached MusicVAE [53] which was trained over significantly more data. Given that the performance of transformers depends strongly on scale [88], training a larger model on a larger dataset will almost certainly improve the quality of the models.

5.2 Future Work

There are many possible avenues for future work on this topic. To begin, one could recreate our experiments with different sequence lengths and resolutions. This would expand the opportunities of the types of relationships we can look for as well as the level of rhythmic nuance that we are able to observe.

On the topic of music perception, this work does not attempt to answer questions like, "What makes two rhythms compatible?" One could explore this question by conducting a study of the model's inner workings, for example by studying a detailed visualization of the sequence positions that the model is attending to as it generates each token, as presented in [10] and shown in Figure 16. It would be illuminating to examine both the self-attention and cross-attention heads of the model as this would tell us what the model is paying attention to in Part A when generating Part B. At which sequence positions does the model attend to the strong or weak beats? In what scenarios does the model attend exclusively to one part?

Figure 16: Visualized self-attention showing which notes in the past are informing the future. Figure from [10].

Another natural extension of this work would be to model the relationships between additional parts, such as drums-melody and drums-bass. The addition of a drums part would require either a method for flattening polyphonic drum patterns into monophonic sequences in a way that preserves the perception of rhythm, or the use of a polyphonic sequence representation. Such an extension may also shed light on methods for annotating parts that are more sophisticated than our approach of extracting melodies as uninterrupted sequences of monophonic notes. This could open the door to modeling other polyphonic parts in the Lakh MIDI dataset, such as harmony.

Aside from contemporary western music, there are many other styles of music with multiple parts. It would be interesting to investigate the relationships present between, for example, the Square-Triangle-Noise parts in video game music using the LakhNES dataset [18] or the various parts in symphonic classical music in the MusicNet dataset [89].

The ultimate aim of this research is to contribute to creative applications such as composition tools and mashup creation systems. Incorporating these models into such applications would facilitate the subjective evaluation of our models in creative contexts, thereby paving the way for further inquiries.

List of Figures

1	An excerpt from <i>Tonight</i> by Leonard Bernstein with a grouping of instruments to parts. Transcription from the Lakh MIDI Dataset [1].	2
2	Onset vectors. Figure from [33].	6
3	Examples of event-based representations for a musical excerpt. Figure from [32].	6
4	29 descriptors for six distinguished rhythms. Figure from [33].	8
5	The edit distance between the <i>clave son</i> and the <i>fume-fume</i> rhythm is 4. Figure from [33].	10
6	An illustration from [48] showing the 13 classes of temporal relations defined by Allen [47].	10
7	A visualization from [48] illustrating an excerpt from Haydn String Quartet Op. 17 No. 3 Mvt. 1, reorganized to show the structure of a graph created using temporal relations between notes.	10
8	Overview architecture of our sequence-to-sequence transformer model.	18
9	A distribution of language token probabilities. Figure from https://huggingface.co/blog/how-to-generate	20
10	Input melodic rhythms (top) with generated bass rhythms (bottom).	23
11	Descriptor distributions for training set bass rhythms ($n = 10000$) vs generated bass rhythms ($n = 100$) for the MTB model with nucleus sampling (top) and the baseline model (bottom).	24
12	Input bass rhythms (top row) with generated melodic rhythms (bottom row).	25
13	Descriptor distributions for training set melodic rhythms ($n=10000$) vs generated melodic rhythms ($n=100$) for the BTM model with nucleus sampling (top) and the baseline model (bottom).	27
14	Paired descriptor distributions for melody and bass rhythm pairs from the training set ($n=10000$) vs each model ($n=100$).	28
15	Two bass rhythms that are perceptually similar, with repeated notes preserved (left) and removed (right).	30
16	Visualized self-attention showing which notes in the past are informing the future. Figure from [10].	31

List of Tables

1	The vocabulary used to tokenize onset vectors.	17
2	Pairwise distribution similarity measures for generated bass rhythms, averaged across all descriptors.	25
3	Pairwise distribution similarity measures for generated melodic rhythms, averaged across all descriptors.	26
4	Pairwise distribution similarity measures for melody-bass pairs, averaged across all paired descriptors.	28

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